

Compensation is neither a Mercy nor a Bounty, but is a Constitutional Obligation: Examination of the Indian Criminal Justice System in View of the Constitutional and Judicial Perspectives¹

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Abstract

Few researchers argue that the ancient system of compensating damages to the victims of violence has gradually lost its significance from the time of colonial rule as it focused mainly on prosecuting the criminals rather than restoration of victims. The victim is considered as a witness to the offence² to prove the guilt of the accused only. The criminal justice system (CJS) is under the postulation that the crime victims would adequately satisfy with the sentence of wrongdoers. Such assumption is adversely impacting the wellbeing of the survivors of the crime victims and their dependents³. The Indian Constitution has been criticized that it does not contain any explicit provision requiring the wellbeing of the crime victims, and that their restoration is at the mercy of the law enforcing agencies. Therefore, the authors in this study examine significant constitutional provisions alongside judicial perspectives, and argue that the Indian law adequately provisioned for rehabilitation and restoration of crime victims. Their study concludes that considerable amount of weightage has been given in India by the Constitution to acknowledge that the CJS

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²Anoop Kumar and Mudit Soni, Legal Regime on Victim Compensation in Britain, USA and India: A Comparative Historical Perspective and Way Forward, *Dehradun Law Review* (2024), Vol. 16(1), pp. 145-163.

³Bharti Manglani, Victim Compensation Scheme- Shortcomings & Recommendations, available at: <https://cdnbbsr.s3waas.gov.in/s37a68443f5c80d181c42967cd71612af1/uploads/2025/03/20250319598301777.pdf> (accessed on Oct. 21, 2025).

is victim-centric, and that compensation to the crime victims is neither a mercy nor a bounty but is a constitutional obligation on the State for their swift restoration.

Keywords

Compensation, Crime Victims, Criminal Justice System, Rehabilitation, Restoration.

1. Introduction

Compensation has become an integral part of the Criminal Justice System (CJS) in any human society as it plays a crucial role in the restoration of victims of violence. Though the verdict of the Supreme Court of India (SCI) in 2011 in *Baldev Singh v. State of Punjab case*⁴ allowing compounding of non-compoundable offence was criticized as a violation of law and of constitutional morality⁵, it underscored the importance of reparation to women victims to go back to their previous position that they were enjoying prior to the offence than punishing the offenders even in grave sexual offences such as rapes and gang-rapes. Again, in the recent past, the India's Apex Court in 2024 in *Saibaj Noormohammad Shaikh v. State of Maharashtra case*⁶ has viewed that while sentencing or acquitting the accused, the Sessions Courts are under mandatory obligation to award reparation to the victim-survivors who are especially the women and minors affected by sexual violence⁷. This outlook has outlined the accountability of the Trial Courts for granting interim compensation, as well as the responsibility of the Legal Services Authorities (LSAs) for ensuring quick payment to crime victims⁸. Given to this, it can be understood that payment of compensation to the crime victims is not a bounty, but it is a fundamental obligation on the Courts to ensure that it is paid adequately by the State to get crime victims rehabilitated swiftly even in the situations of sentencing or non-sentencing or non-tracing of the wrongdoers.

2. Need for the Study

Inspite of the (i) well-structured constitutional goals, (ii) adoption of the United Nations Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power (1985)⁹, (iii) well-framed policies by the Indian Legislature and the Executive, and (iv) the law settled by the nation's Apex Court - it appears that the crime victims in India yet often face challenges in getting treated dignifiedly, and in getting sufficient compensation for restoration. The CJS has been facing serious criticism from researchers that the crime victim is often considered as a mere bystander to assist the State to establish the culpability of the wrongdoer. It is overlooking the wellbeing of the crime victims where their needs often go unaddressed while prosecuting the offenders under the customary accused-centric¹⁰ retributive approach of justice. The repercussions of violent offences would leave crime victims with

⁴ Criminal Appeal No. 749 of 2007 (decided on Feb. 22, 2011).

⁵ Aditi Sheth, The Baldev Singh Case: A Flagrant violation of law and of Constitutional Morality, *NLIU Law Review* (2013), Vol.III, pp. 283-303.

⁶ Criminal Appeal No. 4495 of 2024, Special Leave Petition (Crl.) No. 13890 of 2024 (decided on Nov. 11, 2024).

⁷ The Hindu Bureau, Supreme Court directs trial courts to order payment of victim compensation in sexual assault cases, *The Hindu* (Nov. 06, 2024).

⁸ Speed Post Communication of the Supreme Court D. No. 35415/2024 dated Nov. 07, 2024.

⁹ Madhavi Raje, Victim's rights under the Indian Criminal Law System, *iPleaders* (Jun. 12, 2022).

¹⁰ MA Saleem, The victim of crime is treated as a mere witness in the prosecution of the offence, *The Hindu* (Aug. 29, 2024).

unrelenting physical and psychological health issues. The law towards restitution of injured is very deficient (Menon, 2006)¹¹. Hence, the State is suggested to shift its focus to victim-centric restorative justice¹² approach in which the compensation occupies a central point.

3. Research Methodology

The research is a combination of auto-ethnography and empirical study. Primary data has been collected from the corresponding author's observations while handling various sexual offence cases as Judicial Officer, as well as Secretary of the DLSA. The primary data is also included in it the information collected from the public domain, legal documents, research scholars' publications, print media reports, and decisions of the Judiciary. Furthermore, secondary information has been collected through an empirical study using structured questionnaires from 204 victims of sexual offences which include rape against women (74), rape against girls (69), sexual assaults other than rape and acid attacks (58), and acid attacks (03) belong to the Andhra Pradesh State in India, to understand their post-victim living status. 16 victims belong to General Category, 39 belong to Backward Class, 67 belong to Scheduled Caste and 72 belong to Scheduled Tribe communities. 28 belong to Economically Backward Class, 156 belong to financially unsound, and 20 belong to below poverty line. 25 were the physically challenged individuals.

4. Discussion

The crime leads to a lot of adverse impacts on the lives of the victims of sexual offences. The information collected from 204 victims reveal their aftermath challenges as below:

Table 1: Aftermath struggles of crime victims

Response	Loss or damage of body parts	Psychological Issues	Daily functioning	Loss of prospects	Safety and security	Family or community relations	Re-victimization in consequence of offence
Yes	41	146	72	34	135	168	204

¹¹M Nagpal and C Rawandale (2023), Tracing journey of crime victim's position under Indian law with evolutionary insights from the United States' federal code on victims' rights, *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 10(2). <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2023.2286071>

¹²Jim Parsons and Tiffany Bergin, The Impact of Criminal Justice Involvement on Victims' Mental Health, *Journal of Traumatic Stress* (2010), DOI: 10.1002/jts.20505.

Fig.1: Percentage of the no. of "Yes" Responses of Victims on "Crime Impact of on their Living Status".

The above data reveals that every crime victim is suffering from re-victimization in one way or the other. 82% of the victims became isolated because of the offences. 72% are suffering from psychological issues such as depression, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorders and HIV related issues. 20% are suffering from physical injuries such as disfigurement and dermatological complications. The girls who were victimized of rape were compelled to stop their education and career. While collecting information, the researchers understood that the family members of the victims are facing humiliation and abuse from the community severely.

Given to the sympathetic living status of crime victims, the researchers in this study attempted to detect various constitutional provisions and judicial perspectives which seek wellbeing of crime victims and to highlight the liability inflicted on State by the Constitution of India (COI) towards taking effective measures for their restoration.

4.1. Constitutional provisions towards victim wellbeing

The Constitution is acknowledged as the superlative law of the land in India. It aims at securing a just and social order in society. The essence of reparation to crime victims can be extracted from its different provisions¹³ that guaranteed persons for basic rights and public assistance in unwanted situations. Every act or lapse which may lead to disgrace or injustice or inequality or prejudice invites the fury of the Constitution¹⁴. The constitutional functionaries i.e. the Legislature, the Executive and the Judiciary are imposed with a responsibility of striving for efficient measures in prevention of every act of violence that may lead to victimization of any individual, and for rehabilitation and integration of victims and wrongdoers¹⁵.

13Deepak Sabherwal, Legal Provisions On Compensation To Victims Of Crime. *Law Finder Live*.

14 Joseph Shine v. Union Of India, AIR 2018 SUPREME COURT 4898.

15Barcelona Panda, Victims Right to Rehabilitation: India, UK and US Experience, *Manupatra*.

Article 12 imposes responsibility on every government institution to secure human dignity. Article 13(2) bars the State from creation of any laws which curtail or confiscate fundamental rights (FRs). Religious vilification, gender disparity, and deprivation of human rights are considered as the acts of unfair treatment or ill-treatment¹⁶. These two provisions together give indication that the State is not provided with a *Right to Sovereign Immunity* and it cannot hop from liability for the act or lapse of its authorities¹⁷, when caused harm to the *right to life and personal liberty* of individuals and to suitably compensate such damage. This provision provides power to the Judiciary to prevent public authorities from victimizing individuals through abuse of rule, arbitrary arrest and detention.

4.1.1. Protection under Right to Equality

The philosophy of the *Preamble* is upholding the dignity of every inhabitant, even a victim of violence, through equality of status and opportunities. Article 14 in juxtaposition with Article 15 articulates that no inhabitant is to be suffered of discrimination or ill-treatment on the reason of social status, sex, age or birthplace, or all of them.

Articles 14 and 15 protect women and children from being victimized of sexual pestering, misuse, inequitable payment of wages, and ill-treatment at workplace. Every sexual pestering or misuse is an infringement of rights to- *gender parity and life and liberty* safeguarded under Article 21¹⁸. The verdict of Apex Court in *Visakha* case based on the provisions of Articles 14, 19 and 21 led to structuring of guidelines in deterrence of sexual pestering at job place. It also led to creation of *Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, Resdressal) Act 2013* offering reparation to victims for rehabilitation and career loss. Article 14 obstructs indifferent treatment based on geological location, and provides maintenance of parity in reparation, requiring similar structure of compensation across the country¹⁹.

4.1.2. Safeguards under Right against Untouchability

Article 17 views that unouchabiity is a denial of human dignity and equality. Hence, it prohibits victimization on untouchability reason. It protects Dalits from victimization of exclusion, economic scarcity and violence. It is the basis for the *Protection of Civil Rights Act of 1955* and the *Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes (Prevention of Atrocities) Act of 1989*. It safeguards the rights of such victims against prejudice and social exclusion. It is a solid assurance for conserving human dignity of weaker sections²⁰.

¹⁶Available at: <https://www.humanrights.vic.gov.au/for-individuals/victimisation/> (accessed on Apr. 6, 2025).

¹⁷Available at: [https://www.mchrdrd.gov.in/splfc2021/subjects/PCCI/2021%20sfc%20State%20\(Article12\)%20\(1\).pdf](https://www.mchrdrd.gov.in/splfc2021/subjects/PCCI/2021%20sfc%20State%20(Article12)%20(1).pdf) (accessed on Jun. 10, 2025).

¹⁸*Vishaka and Others v. State of Rajasthan and Others*, Aug. 13, 1997, Available at: <https://cdnbbsr.s3waas.gov.in/s3ec0490f1f4972d133619a60c30f3559e/uploads/2024/01/2024011635-1.pdf>

¹⁹Ipsita Ojal and Varinder Kaur, *Towards equal justice: Addressing the disparity in victim compensation across Indian states*, *Social Sciences & Humanities Open* (2025), Vol. 11, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.101436>

²⁰ *Indian Young Lawyers Association v. State of Kerala*, (2019) 11 SCC 1.

4.1.3. Privilege under Right to Freedom

Article 19 allows crime victims to share their sufferings leading to awareness and action. It permits them forming groups and advocates each other on their entitlements. They can shift their residences to safer places, and for occupational purposes for sustenance. This provision in combination with Article 21 (right to life) has been viewed as integrated a right to residence²¹. It gives victims a right of being heard, and being informed of all criminal proceedings. Article 19(1) imposes a prima facie compulsion on public authorities to give crime victims all appropriate information²². While highlighting the need of upholding the reliability of judicial process in safeguarding victims' rights, the Apex Court illuminated that the right of crime victims under this provision must not be intruded or shall not be abused the purity of legal proceedings²³.

4.1.4. Protection under Right to Life

Article 21 underscores the compulsion of the State to secure sufficient livelihood to the victims to live with human dignity. It gives victims of undeserved act or omission a right to be provided with adequate means in which reparation is indispensable. The Judiciary is authorized to grant reparation for livelihood as a rehabilitative support either from wrongdoer and or from State to make it adequate²⁴. In *Chairman, Railway Board v. Chandrima Das*²⁵ case, SCI outlined that sexual abuse is a breach of *right to life* since it pushes the victim into deep psychological trauma, and such victims are to be suitably compensated to live with dignity. In *Bodhisattwa Gautam v. Subhra Chakraborty*, and in *Zee Tele Films Ltd. v. Union of India*²⁶, it construed that right to life provision can even be enforced horizontally against non-State bodies or persons to suitably compensate the victims²⁷. In *Piyali Dutta v. The State of West Bengal*²⁸ case, the West Bengal High Court opined that victims have a right to receive fair reparation in terms of Article 21 which guarantees *Right to Live with Dignity*. In *M.H. Hoskot v State of Maharashtra*²⁹ case, the SCI held that right to life is included a right to legal aid.

4.1.5. Provision for Compensation

Article 38 solicits public welfare through minimization of inequalities in opportunities, facilities, earnings and status. It is the basis for Sec. 357A of the *Code of Criminal Procedure 1973* (CrPC) which inflicts accountability on State to ensure social justice through sufficient reparation to crime victims. In *Delhi Domestic Working Women's Forum v. Union of India*³⁰ case, the Apex Court applied this provision in

²¹ *U.P. Avas Evam Vikas Parishad v. Friends Cooperative Housing Limited*, 1996 AIR 114, 1995 SCC SUPL. (3) 456.

²² Srijon Banerjee, Victim Compensation and Restorative Justice in India: A Comprehensive Analysis of Progress and Challenges, *GLS Law Journal*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.69974/gslawjournal.v7i1.155>

²³ B Sree Lekshmi, Impact of Media Trial on Rights of Accused and Victim, *SEEJPH* (2024), Vol. XXV (S2), pp. 3494-3503.

²⁴ Rajesh Mahajan, Victim Compensation Laws in India, Chambers and Partners (Apr. 22, 2024), available at: <https://chambers.com/articles/victim-compensation-laws-in-india> (accessed on Apr. 20, 2025).

²⁵ AIR 2000 SC 988; 2000 Cr LJ 1473; 2000 AIR SCW 649.

²⁶ (2005) 4 SCC 649,

²⁷ Neerav Merchant, India's Supreme Court upholds the horizontality of the fundamental right of freedom of speech- Implications on data privacy, Majumdar & Partners (Feb. 7, 2023).

²⁸ W.P. No. 26174 (W) of 2014, Calcutta High Court (Appellate Side), decided on 7 July, 2017

²⁹ AIR 1978 SC 1548.

³⁰ 1995 SCC (1) 14, JT 1994 (7) 183

benefit of crime victims and suggested the State on creation of Criminal Injuries Compensation Board (CICB)³¹.

4.1.6. Provision for Right to Free Legal Aid

Particular segments of community viz., physically challenged persons, females, kids, and downtrodden sections are found at a high risk of victimization of violence (Black et al., 2011; Breiding et al., 2014; Conroy & Cotter, 2017)³² and abuse of power. Most of them are unable to have access to justice system because of poverty, social system, pecuniary and other constraints. To overcome this difficulty, Article 39A has been inserted in the Constitution to offer free legal assistance to needy victims and perpetrators to have access to justice system, to participate in criminal proceedings, and to observe fair investigation and examination. It obligates the State to structure and strengthen schemes benefitting helpless crime victims, and to make them aware of their rights to reliefs. It shows the commitment of the CJS for providing equal opportunities to the grievance parties to secure equal access to justice. It is the basis for enactment of *The Legal Services Authorities Act 1987*, and constitution of *National Legal Services Authority (NALSA)* to oversee the implementation of legal aid system in the country³³. It also led to creation of *The Rights of Persons with Disabilities Act 2016* for providing equal access to justice to the persons with disability.

4.1.7. Right to privilege under “Vulnerable Sections of Society”

The Judiciary has extensively widened the constitutional scope of this expression contained in Article 16 for social integration of crime victims. One of the objective of this provision is empowerment of females who are the most deprived sections, through every possible step³⁴, and to enhance maximum assistance in the form of instruction and employment to the injured of family sadism or sexual offence³⁵.

4.1.8. Right to Compensation for Recovery of Economy

Article 41 obligates the State to extend social support, pecuniary and or otherwise, to the persons when they are facing incapacitation and undeserved wants. It requires the State to prevent discrimination in the early stage by understanding apprehension of crime victims. It is an imperative tool of the crime victims to get State's aid for recovery of economy³⁶.

³¹Shalini Goel and Prem Chandra, Right to Compensation Under Constitutional Scheme in India, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.* (2025), 2 (4), 328-334, doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15212555>

³²A Mailhot Amborski, et al., Sexual Violence Against Persons With Disabilities: A Meta-Analysis. *Trauma Violence Abuse.* (2022), 23(4):1330-1343. doi: 10.1177/1524838021995975

³³Issues in implementation of free legal aid schemes – Critical Analysis of Article 39A of the Constitution of India, *iPleaders* (Aug. 9, 2018).

³⁴Naresh Rout and Jayashree Bez, Women's Rights and Violence in India: A Study of Constitutional Safeguards, *Odisha Review* (2017).

³⁵Available at: <https://www.unodc.org/e4j/en/crime-prevention-criminal-justice/module-11/key-issues/3--the-right-of-victims-to-an-adequate-response-to-their-needs.html> (accessed on: Jun. 16, 2025).

³⁶Pawar Shivprasad Vijay, Constitution of India and Compensation to Victim of Crime Under Victim Rights, *IJRPR* (2024), Vol. 5 (4), pp 6056-6063.

4.1.9. Right to Free from Hunger and Starvation

Article 39(a) obligates State to realize sufficient livelihood to citizens. Article 47 obligates it to take steps to constantly improve public health by making people to have access to nutritional food. Article 21 obligates it to ensure people leading a standard life. These stipulations together give crime victims a right to be safeguarded from hunger starvation in case of their incapacitation during unwanted circumstances. They impose obligations on State to initiate every possible measure for thwarting mass disasters resulting to mass victims, and to ensure readiness for zero-tolerance victimization, and endeavor support for restoration of people in case of victimization. These conditions laid a foundation to the creation of the *Protection of Human Rights Act 1993*³⁷.

4.1.10. Right to Health for Speedy Recovery from Illness

In addition to Article 47 soliciting State to secure public health and improve nutritional levels of people, Article 243G is another provision which mandates the State to provide potable drinking water, sanitation services, and women and kid growth programs. These amenities play crucial role in improving health status of victims of violence at basic level³⁸. This provision can be linked with Article 21 (*right to life*) in which the right to health is integrated in it, to obligate the State for extending free medical aid, clean surrounding, adequate food, and appropriate dwelling without prejudice to go back to previous position.

4.1.11. Right to Fair Investigation and Fair Trial

Articles 20 and 21 are associated with each other to provide entitlement to perpetrators and crime victims as well, for fair investigation and fair trial since the State is obligated to secure equitable justice, peace and harmony³⁹.

4.1.12. Right to Constitutional Remedies

Articles 32 and 226 made available remedies to the citizens to solicit intrusion of the High Court at State level, and SCI at national level for justice if their FRs are infringed and they suffered loss, corporeally, pecuniary or psychologically or any other form. These provisions gave unrestricted authority to these Courts to exercise *suo motu* power⁴⁰ to intervene into the unjust situations, and to award suitable reparation to affected persons. The extent and enforcement of writ reparation can be widened through efficient measures without restricting it to the incidents of FRs infringement⁴¹.

4.1.13. State's Responsibility for infraction of FRs

Article 300(1) puts vicarious liability on State for acts and lapses of its officials when infringed to FRs of people. It gives right to affected person to sue the State and claim damages. In *N. Nagendra Rao &*

³⁷Available at: <https://nhrc.nic.in/press-release/right-food-fundamental-right> (accessed on Apr 5, 2025).

³⁸Ravinder Kumar, Strict Implementation of the Right to Health as a Fundamental Right: ensuring Universal Access and Equity in India, *Law and Safety* (2024), № 2 (93), DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32631/pb.2024.2.14>

³⁹Parminder Kaur, Fair Investigation: Backbone of Criminal Justice System, *The Haryana Police Journal* (2020), Vol.3. pp. 33-39.

⁴⁰Shalini Goel and Prem Chanda, Right to Compensation under Constitutional Scheme in India, *IJSRT* (2025), Vol. 2(4).

⁴¹Sushila Rao, Constitutional Rights Violations and Compensatory Jurisprudence in India and U.S.A.: Justifications and Critique, *NLSIR* (2006), Vol.18 (1), pp. 93-111.

*Company v. State of Andhra Pradesh*⁴² case, the Apex Court clarified that the doctrine of sovereign immunity does not free the State from payment of damages to crime victims as it stands diluted in modern days⁴³.

4.1.14. Provision for preventing unjust outcomes in heinous crimes

Article 136 authorizes SCI to uphold rule of law. It can exercise its jurisdiction for allowing the concerns at the plea of parties, or on its own through *suo motu*, if deems fit⁴⁴, and may sanction leave to any person, even not a party⁴⁵ or can interfere into the decisions of any court of law by bypassing the normal appellate procedure, in prevention of miscarriage of justice⁴⁶. In *PSR Sadhanantham v. Arunachalam*⁴⁷ case, the SCI enlarged the scope of this provision by stating that it provides entitlement to the legal heir of the victim or of a high-minded person to seek justice to the victim or victim-dependents, and is a prominent instrument to any citizen who wishes to elicit legal process for justice to neighbors. In *Tamil Nadu Electricity Board v. Sumathi and Others*⁴⁸ case, the top court held this provision a powerful tool empowering affected parties to claim comprehensive justice.

4.1.15. Provision for Complete Justice to Victims

Article 142 is acknowledged as a strong weapon given to SCI for providing inclusive justice to the affected parties. It has authorized SCI to rectify system's failures, to mitigate trauma of injured⁴⁹, and to prioritize victim's rehabilitation attaching with the convict in constitutional lines⁵⁰. It gives extraordinary discretion to SCI to uphold due procedure to deliver complete and fair justice⁵¹ and to make sure that the affected individuals are provided with good accommodation, improved instruction, skillful training and job to enable them to integrate into society.

4.1.16. Backbone provision for fair justice

Article 50 provides judicial autonomy and prevents abuse of authority in governance. It intends protection of civil liberties, taking independent decisions based on legal merits, and upholding rule of law⁵² which are central elements and vital constituents in the CJS.

⁴²(1994) 6 SCC 2005.

⁴³Sarica Ashok Reddy, Constitutional Torts under Article 300 of the Constitution of India, *Lawyers Club India* (May 22, 2020).

⁴⁴Arthad Kurlekar and Jaimini Vyas, Special Leave Petitions, an impediment to Justice: Need for structural changes to ensure efficient time allocation of the court, available at: <http://docs.manupatra.in/newslines/articles/Upload/23DCCFF6-CEA5-4494-9877-40F3C2ABD219.pdf> (accessed on Jun. 29, 2025).

⁴⁵Justice Mukta Gupta, Concept of Locus Standi in relation to Criminal Jurisprudence. Available at: <https://nja.gov.in/>

⁴⁶Editor, SS Rana & Co, Special Leave Petition (SLP) under Article 136 of the Constitution of India, available at: <https://ssrana.in/litigation/special-leave-petition-india/> (accessed on: Jun. 29, 2025).

47 1980 AIR 856, 1980 SCR (2) 873.

48 AIR 2000 SUPREME COURT 1603, 2000 (4) SCC 543.

⁴⁹Suo Motu WP (C) No. 3 of 2023 with Criminal Appeal No. 1451 of 2024.

⁵⁰Gauri Kashyap, Not a precedent, Supreme Court holds back from sentencing POCSO Convict, *Supreme Court Observer* (May 29, 2025).

⁵¹Pradeep S Mehta and Anushka Kewlani, Complete Justice: Article 142 should be invoked only in truly rare cases, *Livemint* (May 05, 2025).

⁵²Ethan Dumfries, Article 50 of Indian Constitution – Separation of Judiciary from Executive, *The Edu Law* (May 22, 2025).

4.1.17. Provision giving Right to Appeal

Article 134 grants appellate jurisdiction to SCI to decide appeals in criminal cases against abuse of justice in the verdicts of High Courts. It grants powers to SCI to confirm existence of substantial law in the decisions of High Courts while reversing lower court's verdicts or sentencing suspects to death by taking away proceedings from subordinate courts. This stipulation protects persons from grave unjust treatment. In *Kishore Singh v. State of Madhya Pradesh*⁵³ case, the SCI held that a *right to appeal* is accessible to a person if he or she experiences unfairness by the conclusion of High Court. This right is accessible subject to certificate of fitness from High Court as under Article 134A. However, in certain cases, this prerequisite condition is not applicable as per the specific circumstances contained in Article 134(1)(a) and (b), as well as in Sec. 2 of the *Supreme Court (Enlargement of Criminal Appellate Jurisdiction) Act 1970*⁵⁴.

5. Conclusion and Suggestions

The COI contains several provisions which can be made applicable for the upliftment of crime victims. Upon judicious interpretation of various provisions in multiple cases linking with FRs and directive principles, the protector of the COI i.e. the judiciary settled law that victims, regardless of their nationality, are entitled to be restored by the State. They are having constitutional *right to life* in which various allied rights - to health, to livelihood, to medical aid, to legal aid, to shelter, to employment, etc., are integrated in it, to lead a human standard life. It also settled law that the State has a vicarious liability for all the actions and lapses of its officials that lead to violation of FRs, and to pay damages to victims of abuse of power and negligence. Additionally, they are also guaranteed to other human rights which include right to equality and right to freedom as Indian citizens, and thereby are entitled to fair treatment, fair investigation and examination. They are also entitled to be well-informed of their rights and proceedings.

Moreover, the COI contains multiple other regulations obligating State to prevent victimization, to secure just and social order, and to secure social justice. It has granted absolute and extraordinary powers to the Judiciary for preventing or rectifying miscarriage of justice, upholding dignity of every citizen, and ensuring delivery of complete justice so that no individual is deprived of FRs. It has compelled the State to strive to support vulnerable people in disability and unwanted circumstances.

Because of the above requisite obligations, it is concluded that payment of compensation to crime victims is neither a mercy nor a bounty, but it is a constitutional duty of the State to ensure their rehabilitation and recovery of socioeconomic status. Therefore, it should strive towards effectively discharging its obligation for prevention of crimes seriously. It should also strive to strengthen its institutions, to conduct comprehensive empirical studies for identification of crime victims across the country. It should enforce uniform wellbeing schemes and to monitor effective implementation so that no crime victim is left without justice, or in any case to minimize their sufferings that they are yet facing as observed in the model empirical study carried out in this research work.

53AIR 1977 SUPREME COURT 2267, 1977 4 SCC 524.

⁵⁴Justice P Sathasivam, Criminal Jurisprudence of the Supreme Court: Key Highlights, available at: <https://www.tnsja.tn.gov.in/article/CrI%20Jur%20by%20PSJ%20SC.pdf> (accessed on: Jul. 3, 2025).